

PARTIAL CREDIT FOR COMPLICATED ALGEBRAIC EXPRESSIONS

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ABSTRACT

One of the goals of e-Assessment can be seen to replicate the results of marking by hand, including giving partial credit for complicated expressions. STACK provides powerful tools to achieve this. This poster will describe some means of achieving this, with a focus on how we can assess answers with multiple terms in a single answer box (for example an answer which includes both potential and kinetic energy) and how STACK can be made to recognise cases where only some terms are correct.

MOTIVATION & GOALS

A key difficulty of automated e-Assessment compared to more traditional assessment is identifying the specific type of error a student might have made. We wish to do this for two reasons:

- To be able to provide students with useful feedback.
- To be able to fairly allocate marks to students' work.

We can divide errors into two broad categories:

- Made a new error in calculation.
- Carried over an error from a previous part of the question.

STACK is particularly suitable for satisfying both of these requirements for both of these types of errors.

ADVANTAGES OF STACK

- Previous student answers can be used as variables to calculate what answer is expected if an error is carried over from the previous part of the question.
- STACK is based on Maxima, which has powerful computer algebra tools to allow errors to be found:
 - We can check if the variables used are the ones expected, or if the answer just differs from expected answer by a constant.
 - If we have a differential equation question, we can put the student's solution back in the equation to check if it satisfies the solution, and they just made a mistake with the conditions.
 - We can look through the terms in a student's solution individually.

CASE STUDY

We look at the this question (adapted from text provided by the course leader):

Q1. A uniform thin straight rod has length L and mass M . It is free to rotate in a vertical plane, about a horizontal axis a distance $\frac{L}{6}$ from one end of the rod. What is the moment of inertia I ?

S1.
$$I = \frac{7L^2M}{36}$$

Q2. Let θ represent the angle by which the rod deviates from its stable equilibrium position. Write down an expression for the total energy E of the rod in terms of M , L , θ , the derivative of θ with respect to time, and the gravitational acceleration g . Ensure that $E=0$ when the rod is in stationary equilibrium

S2.
$$E = \frac{7L^2M\dot{\theta}^2}{72} + \frac{LMg(1 - \cos(\theta))}{3}$$

For Q1 we do marking and feedback as follows:

- We award 1 mark for the correct answer
- We award 0.5 marks if the answer is just a constant numerical coefficient away from the correct answer.
- If the answer is completely wrong, we check what variables the student used, and give them feedback on whether they were correct or not.

For Q2 we want to give students partial credit if they only get one of either the PE or KE correct. This is made more difficult by students possibly being able to write the PE as one term, or as two terms. The KE is calculated from the answer to the first question, so we also want to give partial credit for follow-through errors. We can achieve this using the following potential response tree, scanning through all the terms in the students' solutions.

1. We count the number of terms and if there are more than three terms tell the student that we may not be able to detect correct terms.

2. Check each term, and each pair of terms, in the solution and award 0.5 points if one of them corresponds to the correct PE.

3 and 5. Check each term and award 0.5 points if one of them corresponds to the correct KE.

4 and 6. If the correct KE is not found, check if any term corresponds to what we expect the student should have found for the KE based on their answer to the first question (to allow for follow through errors) and award 0.25 if that is the case.

7. If the solution has the correct PE and either the correct KE, or a KE with just a follow through error, penalise the student 0.25 points if they have any additional terms.